

CROSSLINKED CHITOSAN-POLYVINYL ALCOHOL BLEND BEADS FOR REMOVAL AND RECOVERY OF Cr (II) FROM WASTEWATER

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ABSTRACT

Crosslinked chitosan/poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) blend aqueous solution was suspended in toluene-chlorobenzene to form droplets. Some of the water then distilled out as azeotropes with the aromatic hydrocarbons to reduce the water content of the suspension droplets. Glutaraldehyde was finally added to the suspension to result in the cross linked chitosan/PVA beads with low water content and high mechanical strength. In addition, prepared crosslinked beads were characterized by FTIR, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) the efficiency of crosslinked chitosan/PVA bended bead as an adsorbent for the removal of Cr (II) from water was studied. It was found to exhibit substantial adsorption capacity over a wide range of initial Cr (II) ion concentration. Effect of time, temperature pH, adsorbent dose and the concentration of adsorption of Cr (II) were investigated by batch process. Pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-order model were evaluated. The kinetics data for the adsorption process follow the second order rate equation. The equilibrium studies data could be described well by the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. The thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 , ΔS^0 , are calculated. It was found that the values ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 increase while the values ΔG^0 decline with rise in temperature. Thus the adsorption process was found to be endothermic and spontaneous. The maximum adsorption Cr (II) ion (76.51%) in pH range 5-6 indicated that material could be effectively utilized for the removal of Cr (II) ion from waste water. The adsorption study showed 62% recovery of Cr (II), when 0.1 EDTA solutions were used as an effluent.

KEYWORDS: Chitosan/PVA beads, Adsorption, Cr(II)ion, Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms etc.

1. *INTRODUCTION*

There are growing interest in developing natural renewable, and low cost adsorbent alternatives to synthetic polymer for the removal of heavy metal ions from wastewater. Chitosan is the alternative from N-deacetylation of chitin, the major component of the shells of crustacean organisms and the second most abundant naturally occurring biopolymer next to the cellulose. Chitin and chitosan have biological and chemical properties such as non-toxicity, biocompatibility, high chemical reactivity, chirality, chelation and adsorption properties¹. The presence of amine group makes chitosan unique among heavy metal ions². Ion exchangers or adsorbents have potential applications in waste water treatments to remove heavy metal ions³ and dye removal⁴. In recent years, polymer blending has been become a method for providing polymeric material with desirable properties for practical applications. In particular, chitosan blended with poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) has been reported to have good mechanical and chemical properties and, as a topic of great interest, has been extensively studied in the biochemical field⁵. Chitosan bead have been used sorption columns. The uses of chitosan beads as an adsorbent also provide the potential for regeneration after sorption and reuse of the beads in subsequent sorption operations. The production of chitosan hydrogel beads involves dissolution of chitosan in an acetic acid solution followed by precipitation process of injecting the chitosan solution in droplets in to the dilute sodium hydroxide solution⁶. However, the hydrogel beads have the disadvantage of poor chemical resistance and mechanical strength. This disadvantage significantly reduces the recycle life of the chitosan beads. To improve these properties, crosslinking of chitosan beads with glutaraldehyde, epichlorohydrin or ethylene glycol glycidyl ether has been commonly used^{7,8}. These crosslinked chitosan beads are still highly swollen in water. Thus, the mechanical strength of the wet beads is still quite poor. The poor mechanical strength of these chitosan beads has significantly limited their practical applications. In addition this crosslinking process has been performed by the reaction of the amino functional group of the chitosan with these cross linkers. As the consequence, the chemical property of the amino functional group has changed up on cross linking.

Heavy metal is essential in small amount for the normal development of animals and plants but most of them are toxic at higher concentrations. Heavy metals are generally introduced in to the environment through natural phenomena and human activities⁹. The contamination of the existing water resources is increasing day by day with increasing industrialization. The disposal of the waste water containing heavy metal is always a

challenging task for environmentalist¹⁰. Effective removal of heavy metal ion from aqueous solution is important in the protection of environmental quality and public health¹¹. There are various methods are available for removal of heavy metal and organic pollutants from industrial wastewater such as precipitation, electrochemical reduction, ion exchange, membrane filtrations and reverse osmosis¹² but these method involve large liquid surface and long desorption time. Cromium has been classified as a toxic heavy metal that can cause serious damage to the kidney and bones. The WHO (world health organization) has recommended the maximum permissible limit of 0.005 mg l⁻¹ Cromium in drinking water. Numerous chitosan based beads¹³ have already been explored for the removal of Cromium ion from aqueous solution. In the present study, prepared cross linked chitosan beads with low water content, high mechanical strength and uncharged amino functional group and used as the adsorbent for the removal and recovery of Cr (II) from waste water.

2. EXPERIMENTAL:

2.1 CHEMICAL AND REAGENTS

Chitosan (100% deacetylation and 20×10^5 g mol⁻¹ molecular weight) was received from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals and used as obtained. Poly (vinyl alcohol) (M_w125,000), tween-80, acetone, methanol, Cromiumnitrate, glutaraldehyde solution, toluene, chlorobenzene, acetic acid, hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide. Etc. of AR grade were S.D. fine Chemicals, India and were used without any further purification.

2.2 PREPARATION OF CROSSLINKED CHITOSAN/PVA BLEND BEADS

Chitosan solution (4.0%, w/w) was prepared by dissolving 4.0 g of chitosan into 100 g of dilute acid (2% w/w). PVA solution (12.5%, w/w) was prepared by dissolving 12.5 g of PVA in 100 ml of distilled water. After that chitosan and PVA solution were mixed properly on magnetic stirrer with constant stirring. A homogeneous polymer gel blend solution with 2/1 (w/w) ration of chitosan to PVA was obtained. The pH value of the blend solution was adjusted to pH 2 by adding concentrated HCl (1.0 ml). The resulting blended solution of PVA and chitosan was suspended in 100 ml of toluene chlorobenzene (1/3, v/v) containing 1.5 g of Tween-80 in a 250 ml three-neck round bottom flask with stirring speed of 150 rpm. Then the system temperature was raised gradually 90°C to distil out a 13.1 ml of water as an azeotrope with the aromatic hydrocarbons to reduce the water content of the suspension droplets. The resulting mixture was cooled to room temperature. A 0.33 g of 50% glutaraldehyde solution was added to the flask and the stirring continued at room temperature

for 8h. The resulting beads were filtered off, washed several times with acetone, suspended in 4% NaOH aqueous solution for 8 h, and then rinsed thoroughly with water until neutral pH.

2.3 ADSORBATE SOLUTION

Stock solution of Chromium was prepared (1000 mg^l-1) by dissolving the desired quantity of Pb(NO₃)₂ · H₂O in distilled water.

2.4 FTIR, XRD, TGA AND SEM STUDIES

The Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of beads were recorded with spectrum GX series 49387 by KBr method. Wide angle X-ray diffractograms of the blend beads were recorded using Philips Xpert X-Ray diffractometer with Cu K α (1.54056) radiation. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM), gold sputter coating were carried out on the desired beads samples at pressure ranging in between 1 and 0.1 Pa. Sample was loaded in the machine, which was operated at 10⁻² to 10⁻³ Pa with EHT 15.00 kV with 300V collector bias using Leo microscope SEMs were recorded. Thermal degradation processes and thermal stability of the beads were investigated using thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) (Mettler Toledo TGA/SDTA851^c with star^c software) under a nitrogen atmosphere using heating rate of 10⁰C min⁻¹ from 50 to 600 ⁰C.

2.5 DISSOLUTION/PVA AND CROSSLINKED CHITOSAN/PVA AND CROSSLINKED CHITOSAN/PVA BEADS

Chitosan/PVA and crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads were tested, which related to their solubility in each of 4% acetic acid, distilled water and 0.1M NaOH. The 0.5 g of Chitosan/PVA without crosslinking and crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads was suspended in each of the diluted acid, distilled water and alkaline solutions for a period of 24 h with constant stirring. The swelling study of crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads was carried out in distilled water at room temperature for a time period of 24 h. Wet crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads (0.5 g) were dried in an oven at 100 ⁰C for 2 h. The percentage swelling of the beads was calculated as:

$$\text{Percentage swelling} = \frac{(W_{\text{wet}} - W_{\text{dry}})}{W_{\text{dry}}} \quad \text{Percentage swelling} = \frac{(W_{\text{wet}} - W_{\text{dry}})}{W_{\text{dry}}} \quad (1)$$

Where W_{wet}, W_{dry} are the weights of the wet and dry beads, respectively.

2.6 ADSORPTION STUDIES.

Batch process was carried out for adsorption studies. A 0.5 g beads was placed in a conical flask having 50 ml Cr (II)solution and the mixture was shaken in a shaker incubator at 100 rpm. The mixture was then filtered at predetermined time interval and the final

concentration of metal ions was determined by EDTA titration method¹⁴ in the filtrate. Amount of Cr (II) adsorbed was then calculated by subtracting final concentration from initial concentration. Adsorption of Cr (II) by 1 g PVA/Chitosan beads was determined by using the following given equation¹⁵ :

$$q = \frac{(C_i - C_f)}{1000 \times W} \quad q = \frac{(C_i - C_f)}{1000 \times W \times V} \quad (2)$$

Where q represents the amount of Cr(II) adsorbed, C_i and C_f are the initial concentration (mg/ml) of Cr(II) after the adsorption. V is the volume of experimental solution and W is the weight (g) of PVA/Chitosan beads.

Adsorption studies were carried out by varying the adsorbate concentration (10-200 mg l⁻¹), the agitation time (0.5 h – 12h), adsorbent amount (0.1-1.0 g) and adsorption temperature (30, 40 and 50 °C). A series of experiments with pH of the initial Cr(II) solution varying between 2 and 10 (by adding 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NaOH solutions) were also carried out using 0.5 g adsorbent at 30 °C. Adsorption isotherms were studied by varying the initial Cr (II) concentration from 25 to 100 mg l⁻¹ while weight of adsorbent in each experiment was kept constant (0.5 g). Each experiment was repeated three times and results were reported as average of them.

2.7 DESORPTION STUDIES

Batch process was used for the desorption studies with varying amount of adsorbent (0.25 – 1.0 g). The desired amount of adsorbent was taken in a conical flask and treated with 50 ml of Cr(II) solution (50 mg l⁻¹) for 8 h. After adsorption solution was filtered and adsorbent was washed several times with distilled water to remove any excess of Cu (II). It was then treated with 50 ml of 0.1 M HCl, HNO₃, and 0.1 M NaCl and 0.01 M EDTA solutions. The amount of Cr(II) desorbed was then determined as usual. The same procedure was repeated with different adsorbent doses.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 INSTRUMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION OF PVA/CHITOSAN BLEND BEADS

FTIR spectra are a useful tool to identify the presence of certain functional groups in a molecule as each specific chemical bond often has a unique energy absorption band. To understand the nature of Chromium adsorption and identify the possible sites of Chromium binding to the crosslinked chitosan/PVA blend beads, FTIR spectra were taken for the crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads before and after adsorption of Lead. Figure 1 (A & B)

shows there are the possibility of overlapping between the N-H and the O-H stretching vibrations; the strong broad band at $3300\text{-}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the broad region is the characteristic of the N-H stretching vibration. The significant decrease of transmittance in this band region after Cromiumadsorption indicates the N-H vibration was affected due to Cromiumadsorption. Other changes in the transmittances can be observed at the wavenumbers of 1639, 1562, 1428, 1383, 1140 and $597.\text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively. These wavenumbers are closely related to the N-H bending, C-N stretchching, acetal stretching, and N-H rocking bands¹⁶. In other words, Cromiumadsorption was found to affect all of the bonds with N atoms, indicating that nitrogen atoms are the main adsorption sites for Cromiumadsorption on the crosslinked chitosan-PVA beads.

In fact, the FTIR data showed that the N-H bending vibration wave numbers at 1644 and 1562 cm^{-1} before Laed adsorption were shifted to 1634 and 1553 cm^{-1} after Cromiumadsorption, which suggest that the attachment of Cromiumto nitrogen atoms that reduced the vibration intensity of the N-H bond due to the molecule weight becoming heavier after Cromiumattachment.

WXRd pattern of the crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads is shown in Fig.2. From the XRD pattern, it is clear that crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads are amorphous in nature¹⁷. SEM images of the dried crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads before and after the Cromiumadsorption are shown in Fig.3. Beads were dried slowly in two steps, because quick drying may disturb surface morphology of the beads due to fast evaporation. SEM images show that the addition of PVA indeed made the beads become much denser (Fig.3.(A)) and the accumulation of Cromiumtake place on the surface of beads after the adsorption as shown in Fig.3(B)¹⁸.

Figure 1: (A & B) FTIR Spectra of PVA/Chitosan blend beads

Figure 2: XRD pattern

Figure 3: (A & B) SEM image of PVA/Chitosan blend beads

3.2 DISSOLUTION AND SWELLING OF CHITOSAN/PVA AND CROSSLINKED CHITOSAN/PVA BEADS

It was shown that after the crosslinking chitosan/PVA beads were insoluble in acidic and alkaline medium as well in distilled water as supported by observations were recorded in Table1. It is well known that the enhance property attribute to the interactions between chitosan and the PVA in the blend through hydrophobic side chain aggregation and intermolecular hydrogen bonding. The swelling behavior of chitosan/PVA beads was also improved. It is confirmed by the swelling behavior of crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads in dilute acetic acid solution. Thus, the crosslinking treatment is necessary to emphasize the chemical stability of beads in acidic medium. Meanwhile, the less swelling behavior of crosslinked beads was important so that they can be used in an adsorption column. The percentage swelling of chitosan/PVA and crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads are given in Table1.

3.3 ADSORPTION MECHANISMS

For the crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads used in this study, it may be expected that the only adsorption sites for Chromium are at the nitrogen atoms of the amino groups in chitosan and the oxygen atoms of the hydroxyl groups in both chitosan and PVA. Either nitrogen and oxygen atoms have a lone pair or lone pairs of electrons that can bind a proton or a metal ion through an electron pair sharing to form a complex. Because of the stronger attraction of the lone pair of electrons to the nucleus in an oxygen atom than in a nitrogen atom, the nitrogen atoms would have a greater tendency to donate the lone pair of electrons for sharing with a metal ion to form a metal complex than the oxygen atoms. On this consideration, the

following chemical reactions maybe proposed to account for the adsorption of Chromium on the crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads:

Where R represents all other components except- NH_2 in crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads. The equilibrium of the reaction in eq 3 was usually established according to the initial solution pH values. When Chromium ions were added into the solution, the reaction in eq 4 started, due to the sharing of the lone pair of electrons from the nitrogen atom with Lead, with a similar mechanism to that of the reaction in eq.3. However, the binding of a Chromium ion to a nitrogen atom can be expected to be stronger than the binding of a H^+ to a nitrogen atom (i.e., protonation of the amino group) because the electrical attraction force between the lone pair of electrons from the nitrogen atom and the divalent nitrogen atom and the monovalent proton (H^+). This difference in the binding force drives the reaction in eq 5 to take place through a competitive adsorption of Cr^{2+} over H^+ to the nitrogen atom, which may sometimes be considered as an ion exchange mechanism¹⁹ The reaction in eq 5 however can be expected to be slower than the reaction in eq 4, attributed to the smaller the N in R-NH_3^+ and Cr^+ as compared to the force between the N in R-NH_2^+ and Cr^{2+} . In addition to this, the complexes of $\text{R-NH}_2\text{Cr}^{2+}$ are subject to the reaction in eq 6, due to the greater binding force of Cr^{2+} with the $-\text{OH}$ group from water than with the nitrogen of the amino group in chitosan.

3.3 EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION

Crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads are an effective adsorbent over a wide range of initial Cr(II) concentration. When the initial Cr (II) concentration was increased from 10 to 50 mg l^{-1} , the adsorption remains maximum (76.5%) and decrease to 62% only when initial concentration is further increased from 100-200 mg l^{-1} as shown in Fig. 4. The adsorbent can be utilized effectively for the removal of Cr (II) from water at lower as well as higher initial concentration (100 mg l^{-1}) of Lead.

3.4 EFFECT OF CONTACT TIME

The effect of contact time on the adsorption of at 50 mg l^{-1} initial Cr (II) concentration is shown in Fig. 5. The rate of adsorption is very fast initially and maximum removal of Cr (II) occurs within 4 h followed by a slow increase until state of equilibrium was reached. The necessary time to reach this equilibrium was 8 h and further increase in

equilibrium time up to 24 h showed no change in adsorption. Thus, the equilibrium time was maintained at 8 h in subsequent adsorption study. These observations were in agreement with the work reported earlier with the other metal ion biomaterial system. The initial fast adsorption may be explained as uptake of Cr (II) through physical adsorption since adsorption phenomenon characteristically tends to attain instantaneous equilibrium. The active sites in the system are a fixed number and each active site can adsorb only one ion through an electron pair sharing to form a complex with free- NH^2 group available in crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads and therefore metal adsorption by the adsorbent surface is rapid initially and then decreases as the availability of active sites decreases, thus slowing down the transfer of metal ion from bulk solution to adsorbent surface. The rate of metal removal is of great significance for developing adsorbent-based water technology. The ability of beads to absorb maximum amount of Cr (II) within 4 h min indicates that it is an effective biosorbent for the removal of Cr (II) from waste water.

3.5 EFFECT OF pH

Adsorption of Cr (II) at pH 2 is 44% and increases with increase of pH attaining maximum value in the pH range 4-5 (Fig. 6). In acidic medium (pH2) hydrogen ions compete with metal ions as a result active sites (amine groups) available in beads become protonated resulting the prevention of metal ions adsorption on the surface of adsorbent. However, with increase in pH, more and more negatively charged surface of the adsorbent becomes available and hence uptake of metal ions increases Adsorption of Cr (II) thus increases significantly as pH is increased (72.12% at pH 5). It is known that with the increase in pH, the solubility of metals decreases resulting in their precipitation as hydroxides. The precipitation of Cr (II) as hydroxide was found to occur basic solution, therefore all adsorption studies were carried out at or below pH 5, which is much below the precipitation pH of Cr (II).

3.6 EFFECT OF ADSORBENT DOSE

The adsorption density and percentage adsorption of Cr (II) on crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads is shown in Fig.7. The initial Cr (II) concentration was taken as 50 mg l^{-1} and the adsorbent dose was varied from 0.1 to 1.0 g at constant temperature ($30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The percentage adsorption increases from 30 to 76% but adsorption density decrease from 36.5 to 12.53 mg g^{-1} when adsorbent dose is increased. The decrease in the adsorption density is due to the fact that some of the adsorption sites remain unsaturated when adsorbent dose is

increased. On the other hand more and more Cr (II) is adsorbed as the number of available adsorption sites are increased resulting in the overall increase in the removal efficiency.

Figure 4: Effect of concentration

Figure 5: Effect of contact time

Figure 6: Effect of pH

3.7 ADSORPTION KINETICS

The rate constants were calculated by using pseudo-first order and pseudo-second-order kinetic models¹⁸. The first order expression is given as:

$$\log(q_e - q)^n = \log q_e - \frac{K_1}{2.303t} \log(q_e - q)^n = \log q_e - \frac{K_1}{2.303t} \quad (7)$$

Where q_e is the amount of metal ions adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent at equilibrium or adsorption capacity (mg g^{-1}), q the amount of Cr (II) adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent at any given time t . K^1 is the rate constant. The values of K^1 were calculated from slope of the linear plot of $\log (q^e - q)$ versus t at various concentrations as presented in Fig. 7 (A). The values of regression coefficient (R^2) and rate constants at various concentrations are given in Table 2.

The pseudo-second-order kinetic rate equation is given as

$$\frac{t}{q} = \left(\frac{1}{h}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{q_e}\right) t \quad \frac{t}{q} = \left(\frac{1}{h}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{q_e}\right) t \quad (8)$$

Where $h = K_2 q_e^2$ and K_2 are the rate constant of pseudo-second order adsorption (g mg^{-1}). The values of h were calculated from the y intercept of the linear plots of t/q versus t at various initial Cr (II) concentrations as presented in Fig. 7 (B). The values of K_2 and h are reported in Table 2. It is evident from table 2 that the prepared beads followed second order kinetics¹⁶ for the concentration range studied than pseudo-first order kinetics under similar conditions.

3.8 EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE

The temperature range used in this study was from 20 to 40°C. Thermodynamic parameters such as free energy change (G), enthalpy changes (G), enthalpy changes (H) and entropy changes (S) were calculated from the following equation¹³:

$$K_c = \frac{C_{ac}}{C_e} K_c = \frac{C_{ac}}{C_e} \quad (9)$$

Where K_c is the equilibrium constant, C_{AC} are equilibrium concentrations (mg l^{-1}) of Pb (II) on the beads and in the solution, respectively.

$$G^\circ = -2.30 \log K_c \quad (10)$$

Where T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin and R is the gas constant.

$$\log K_c = \left(\frac{S^\circ}{2.303R} \right) - \left(\frac{H^\circ}{2.303RT} \right) \quad \Delta \quad (11)$$

The ΔH° and ΔS° values were calculated from the slope and intercept of Von't Hoff plot of $\log K_c$ versus $1/T$ and their values are recorded in Table 3. It is revealed from Table 3 that ΔH° and ΔS° are increase as the rise in temperature while the values of ΔG° decrease. Thus the Chromium adsorption on crosslinked Chitosan/PVA beads is endothermic in nature. It is also found that the Chromium adsorption is spontaneous and spontaneity increase with rise in temperature. Positive value of ΔS° suggest randomness at the solid-solution interface during adsorption.

3.9 ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS

Adsorption isotherm model describes how adsorbates interact with adsorbents, and comprehensive understanding of the nature of interaction is essential for the most effective use of the adsorbent. It is thus essential to correlate the equilibrium data by either theoretical or empirical models for designing a perfect operation adsorption system for industrial effluents. In the present study, the equilibrium data were derived from the linear form of Freundlich Eq. (12) and Langmuir (Eq. (13)) model of adsorption isotherm:

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad \log q_e = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{K_L} + \frac{a_1}{k_L} C_e \quad \frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{K_L} + \frac{a_1}{k_L} C_e \quad (13)$$

Where C_e is the remaining Cr (II) ion concentration (in mg/l) in solution, q_e the Cr (II) ion concentration (mg/g) in the adsorbent, K_f the Freundlich constant and $1/n$ is the heterogeneity factor. While a_1 and K_L are the Langmuir constants.

Freundlich isotherm describes the heterogeneous system and reversible adsorption. This is not restricted to the monolayer formation. This model predicts that Chromium ion concentration in the adsorbent will increase with increase in Chromium concentration in the solution. On the other hand in the Langmuir mode, it is assumed that intermolecular forces decrease rapidly with distance and this leads to the prediction that coverage of adsorbent by adsorbate is of monolayer type. Further, it is assumed that once an adsorbate molecule or ions

occupies a particular site of the adsorbent, no further adsorption takes place at that site. Theoretically, adsorbent has finite number of sites and once all these sites are occupied by adsorbate further adsorption cannot take place. By plotting of experimental data into linearized form of Freundlich model is place. By plotting of experimental data into linearized form of Freundlich model is depicted in Fig. 8 (A) and data are rescored in Table4, which shows that deviation from linearity if whole concentration range is taken into consideration. This is probably (i) due to the presence of different groups such as amino, hydroxyl, acetyl in the crosslinked Chitosan/PVA beads producing irregular energy distribution in the adsorbent or (ii) by a purely physical adsorption. However, Langmuir model correlated well ($R^2 = 0.996$) when only one line was used to represent the entire range of experimental data as shown if Fig.8 (B) The values of Longmuir constants are derived from the linear curves of Frequndlich model and the value are reported in Table 4. It is concluded that the values a_L increases with rise in temperature, which indicates that strong binding of Cromium ion with $-NH_2$ group. It was also finding that the theoretical monolayer saturation capacity (Q_0) values increases with rise in temperature. Our experimental findings also corroborated the saturation capacities predicted by Langmuir equation at different temperatures.

The essential feature of Langmuir model can be expressed in terms of a dimensionless constant separation factor or equilibrium paramerter (R_L) given by relation:

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_L C_0} \quad R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_L C_0} \quad (14)$$

Where K_L is the Langmuir constant and C_0 is the initial metal ion concentration ($mg\ l^{-1}$). The values of R_L lie between 5.597 and 00.162 (Table 5) for the initial Cr (II) concentration range from 25 to 10 $mg\ l^{-1}$, which indicated that the favorable adsorption (for favorable adsorption the value of R_L should lie between 0 and) 1.

Figure 7: (A & B) Rate of reaction Figure 8: (A & B) Adsorption Isotherm

Adsorption

Concentration (mg l ⁻¹)	Pseudo-first-order kinetics		Pseudo-second-order kinetics		
	K (min ⁻¹)	R ²	K (g mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	q _e (mg g ⁻¹)	h (mg g ⁻¹)
25	0.00621	0.9913	0.00182	23.753	0.1297
50	0.0598	0.9983	0.00087	36.74	0.1386
100	0.00460	0.9925	0.00043	51.813	0.1543

Temperature (°C)	K _F values	1/n values	n
Freundlich equation			
30	23.2	0.694	1.44
40	39.3	0.610	1.61
50	52.8	0.621	1.64
	a _L	K _L	Q ₀ (mg/g)
Langmuir equation			
30	0.0270	2.98	110.374
40	0.0433	4.87	112.471
50	0.0519	7.53	145.081

Table: 1 The percentage swelling of chitosan/PVA and crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads

Table: 2 The values of K₂ and h

Temperature (°C)	⊗S ¹ (kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	⊗H ¹ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	⊗G ¹ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
30	0.0455	13.794	-1.2091
40	0.0532	16.654	-1.7121
50	0.0612	17.505	-2.2695

Table: 3 The ⊗H⁰ and ⊗S⁰ values were calculated from the slop and intercept of Von't Hoff plot of log K_c versus 1/T

3.10 DESORPTION STUDY

Desorption studies will help to reveals the nature of adsorption process and to recover the Cr (II) from cross-linked chitosan beads/PVA beads. Moreover, it also will help to regenerate the beads so that it can be used again to adsorb metal ions. Desorption studies were carried out by using HCl, HNO₃, NaCl and EDTA solution and desorption of Chromium (II) from crosslinked chitosan/PVA beads was 62.4%.

4. CONCLUSION

Crosslinked Chitosan/PVA blend ion-exchange beads exhibited low water contents and high mechanical strength. High chemical resistivity and charged amino functional groups. Biodegradable, low cost and environment friendly in nature.

The kinetics data show that for the adsorption process, pseudo-second-order kinetic model is obeyed better than pseudo- first-order kinetic model. The Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms indicate favorable adsorption. These data would be useful for designing of water treatment plants for the removal of heavy metal ions. The Crosslinked Chitosan/PVA beads can be utilized for the removal and recovery of Cr (II) from wastewater.

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